

Prevalence Of Congenital Diseases In District Mardankhyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan

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Abstract

Congenital diseases are one of the major causes of hospital admission and one of the main reason of deaths in nurseries. There are a lot of work done on congenital malformations finding and prevalence, but less work is present in district Mardan area. The objective was to find out the prevalence of congenital malformations in district Mardan, KPK and its distribution among male and female, its relation to consanguinity, relation to supplementation intake etc. A structure questionnaire consisting of 22 questions were distributed in hospital of district Mardan. 303 individuals were noticed to be congenitally malformed. The questionnaire was easily understandable and distributed in the gynae and pediatrics wards of Mardan medical complex in district Mardan. This study report that males are more affected than females and consanguinity increase the chances of congenital anomalies. 159 males and 144 females are affected with congenital diseases. 42.57% of parents of affected individuals are related by blood. Genetic counseling can be very effective regarding to cousin marriages and supplements intake during pregnancy. For prevention and treatment regular antenatal checkups and prenatal screening are necessary. Exposure to radiations, smoking, alcohol, and pesticides etc are also very dangerous for the fetus. The neurological abnormalities were also found in the congenital malformed children. The reason of the congenital malformations are the cousin marriages, poor socioeconomic level due to which mostly females do not take sufficient supplements like folic acid which are very useful in the formation of fetus. Males are more affected than females. Congenital malformation may affect one, two or more person of the family.

Introduction

The birth anomalies are structural or functional abnormalities which are inherited from parents. The birth anomalies or congenital malformations can be detected after birth but mostly present at the time of birth (Bronberger *et al.*, 2020). Congenital anomalies are mostly considered to associated with social, economic, psychological and damage to the individual or members of the family. Many factors like social, cultural, consanguineous marriages, family size, family planning, law of abortions and religious laws affects the health of a fetus. Maternal diabetes and hypertension are also the risk factors of congenital malformation (Roy *et al.*, 2016) They are mainly due to chromosomal and metabolic abnormalities; the birth defects are of 2 to 3 percent of all births (Kim M. A *et al.*, 2012). About 10% of pediatric hospital admissions have congenital conditions, 18 to 40% have congenital defects of unknown causes (Gillani *et al.*, 2011). There are various factors for congenital anomalies such as lack of proper nutrition, teratogens, chemicals exposure, exposure to radioactivity and other kinds of pesticides and smoking, genetic factors as well environmental factors (Vatankhah *et al.*, 2017). Congenital malformation can be divided into major and minor groups (Costa *et al.*, 2006). Congenital anomalies have emerged on the most common cause of morbidity and mortality, majority of the congenital anomalies had sporadic occurrences while some with familial evidence (Jabeen *et al.*, 2014). Males are more affected than females and neurological disorders are more common than any other congenital malformation (Zahra *et al.*, 2016). The consanguinity rate was detected as 67.7%, only 32.3% mothers of affected individuals were using folic acids and 16.1% of parents were giving history of passive smoking (Khan *et al.*, 2015). Maternal age of 20 to 30 years shows greater prevalence of affected children. In 0.62% of multipara's congenital anomalies were found and in primiparas the ratio was 0.34% of congenital malformed babies (Farkhanda *et al.*, 2017). Women below 20 years of age had 1.11% of children suffering from congenital anomalies and majority of women were mostly between 20 to 30 years of age. The still births are mainly due to the cause of congenital defects and these congenital defects cause morbidity. (Taksande *et al.*, 2010). The main duration for the fetus formation is 3rd to 8th weeks of gestations. In this normal period the organ system formation occurs. During this period better maternal

health and improved living conditions are very necessary for the normal growth of the fetus, it prevents the children from malformation (Parmar *et al.*, 2010). Primary preventive in the form of vaccination, nutrition and drugs can decrease the chances of congenital malformations. In early detection at the very first stage antenatal checkups are necessary (Hussain *et al.*, 2014). The demographic factors such as dietary deficiency, sex, time, social class, and ethnic groups were involved in pathogenesis (Butt *et al.*, 2013). The rate of abnormalities was 2.8% when parents are related by blood while 0.9% cases when parents are not related by blood (Tayebi *et al.*, 2010). Congenital anomalies have emerged on the most common cause of morbidity and mortality. Majority of congenital anomalies had sporadic occurrences while some have familial evidence. Inheritance pattern in most of the familial cases was autosomal dominant (Jabeen *et al.*, 2014). Cousin marriages plays an important role in higher rates of abnormalities and these children must be taken for genetic counseling. Before marriages genetic counseling must be applied not for only cousin's marriages but also for those who have any kind of genetic disorders (Tayebi *et al.*, 2010). The most affected system of the body is cardiovascular system and Genito urinary system. Congenital malformation like aortic stenosis, aortic arch anomaly, cleft lip, cleft pallet, and tracheoesophageal fistula are common. The cardiac congenital anomalies are most common in preterm infants (Egbe *et al.*, 2015). The most common condition was reported as VSD, followed by ASD, patent ductus arteriosus and pulmonary stenosis. Younger the average age of the patients, the higher the incidence of ventricular septal defect and older the average age, the higher the incidence of atrial septal defect (Shafqat *et al.*, 2012). Neural tube defects are also the most common central nervous system abnormalities. Maternal diabetes is also involved in metabolic disorders. Some factors are over maternal age, multiple gestation, maternal hyperthermia, sodium valproate use by women with epilepsy during pregnancy (Feriha *et al.*, 2008).

Material and methods

2.1. Study Area.

2.1.1. District Mardan

The study was conducted in district Mardan Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan. The Mardan region is between 34 ° 05 "to 34 ° 32" in the North and 71 ° 48 "to 72 ° 25" in the East. It is located northeast of the Buner region, north and northwest is the protected area of Malakand, southeast of the Swabi District, south of the Nowshera District and west of the Charsadda District. The total area of the district is 1632 square kilometers. Study area is shown in (**Figure No. 01**).

Figure No. 01: Show the observed study area of district Mardan KP

1.1.2. Sampling Method.

Total of 10000 population has been taken for our survey in district Mardan. 303 have congenital malformed among them. They are affected with different congenital abnormalities. A questionnaire of 22 questions were distributed among guardians of congenital malformed babies. Complete interview was taken from the parents of the affected individuals. The questionnaire was simple and completed within five minutes. Study design selected for our survey was cross sectional study. Still birth was excluded from this survey. Our inclusive criteria include all the individual with congenital abnormalities. Duration of collecting data is about 6 months.

1.1.3. Data Analysis.

Data type was qualitative. Data is taken from the gynae and pediatrics wards of Mardan Medical Complex. Data interpretation was done by Ms. Excel.

Results

Out of 303 completed questionnaires, data shows that 52.47% (159) male and 47.52% (144) female have congenital anomalies. Males are more affected than females. In some cases, both the family members that is male and female may have malformation. Children born with Cesarean section has greater chance of abnormalities. Consanguinity affects the ratio of abnormalities. Due to first cousin marriages the ratio of malformed babies become increases in a family. When parents are related by blood there is greater risk in the children to be malformed. There is greater chance of autosomal recessive genetic diseases. Children whose parents are not first cousins but distantly related have less chance of malformations but higher than those whose parents are not even distantly related. In district Mardan some female due to low socioeconomic level may do not take supplementations in pregnancy due to which the babies may be congenital malformed. Folic acid is the major supplementation before and during the pregnancy because in early development it is very helpful. It prevents major birth defects of the brain and of spinal cord malformation. In our survey 10.23% (31) of cases mothers of affected individual have taken supplements (folic acid) regularly, 57.42% (174) cases have not taken it regularly while 32.34% (98) of mothers have not taken it at all. Also, mothers of diseased individuals have done regular antenatal checkups in only 8.91% cases, the majority are not giving attention to the antenatal checkups. 15.84% have not done it all according to our survey. The anomaly scan also called anatomy scan which is done at 20 to 22 weeks of pregnancy is also not done in some cases of our target population. It is necessary for the examination of the fetal body. In 34.32% of cases mothers of affected individuals have

recurrent miscarriages due to chromosomal abnormalities. The major malformations in our survey are dwarfism, cardiovascular, Rett syndrome, hemophilia, hydrocephalus, gigantism, down syndrome, hydropsfetalis, spina bifida, microcephaly, cerebralpalsy, rickets, achondroplasia, thalassemia, anencephaly and meningomyelocele. The minor malformations detected in our targeted population are cleft palate, blindness, patent ductus arteriosus. Some affected individuals have normal skin while others have rough or cracked skin and wrinkled skin. Teeth are also affected in some individuals, 9.24% have abnormal shaped teeth, 22.11% have colored, 9.57% have less or absent teeth while 59.07% of affected individuals have normal teeth. Alopecia, baldness and hypotrichosis were also found in these affected individuals. About 4.62% complain of hypotrichosis, 2.31% have baldness and 1.32% have alopecia. The fingers were also abnormal, some have fused, extra or short fingers. Pigeon chest, short lower limb, short arms are also seen in the survey. the other comorbidities in these affected individuals include obesity, diabetes, cancer, and cardiovascular disorders.

Table: 1 Characteristics of Congenital malformation

GENDER	
Male	Female
159	144
AGE	
Range(year)	No
0-10	127
11-20	100
21-30	55
31-40	16
Above 40	05
FAMILY MEMBERS AFFECTED	
Persons affected	No of Families
1 person	156
2 persons	41
More than 3 persons	106
SUPPLEMENTATION IN PREGNANCY	
Not Taken	98
Regularly	31
Not Regularly	174
SKIN OF AFFECTED PERSON	
Normal	252
Cracked	35
Wrinkled	16
TEETH OF AFFECTED PERSON	
Normal Shape	179
Abnormal Shape	28
Colored	67
Less/ Absent	29
HAIRS OF AFFECTED PERSONS	
Alopecia	04
Baldness	07
Hypotrichosis	14
Normal	278
FINGERS OF AFFECTED PERSONS	
Extra Fingers	02
Fused fingers	16
Missing	14
Normal Fingers	215
Short Fingers	56
COUNT BONES OF AFFECTED PERSONS	
Deformed limbs	72
Normal	173
Pigeon chest	9
Short arms	21
Short limbs	28
COUNT BODY SHAPE OF AFFECTED PERSONS	

Dwarf	58
Gigantism	5
Irrational body	62
Normal	178
COUNT VISION OF AFFECTED PERSONS	
No vision at all	21
Normal	207
Weak vision	43
Weak vision and hearing	32
COUNT OF MENTALLY AFFECTED PERSONS	
Anencephaly	23
Megacephaly	27
Mentally retarded	92
Microcephaly	42
Normal	119

Figure No: 02 Show the Graphical analysis of age of affected Persons.

Figure No. 03; Shows the Graphical analysis of Supplementation in Pregnancy.

Figure No. 04; Show the Graphical analysis of Skin of affected Persons.

Figure No. 05; Shows the Graphical analysis of teeth of affected Persons.

Figure No. 06; shows The Graphical analysis of Hairs of affected Persons.

Figure No. 07; Shows the Graphical analysis of Fingers of affected Persons.

Figure No. 08; Shows the Graphical analysis of Bones of affected Persons.

Figure No. 09; Shows the Graphical analysis of body shape of affected Persons.

Figure No. 10; Shows the Graphical analysis of vision of affected Persons.

Figure No. 11; Shows the Graphical analysis of Mentally affected Persons.

Table 2: shows the prevalence of congenital diseases in district Mardan Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan.

S. No	Malformations in patients	Percentages of malformations	No
01	Hydrops fetalis	2.31	07
02	Cleft palate	1.98	06
03	Spina bifida	0.06	02
04	Congenital Hyperparathyroidism	1.32	04
05	Microcephaly	8.91	27
06	Cerebral palsy	1.32	04
07	<i>Rickets</i>	3.96	12
08	Achondroplasia	1.32	04
09	Thalassemia	9.90	30
10	Anencephaly	7.26	22
11	Dwarfism	17.82	54
12	Cardiovascular	2.31	07
13	Rett syndrome	1.65	05
14	Hemophilia	1.98	06
15	Blindness	5.61	17

16	Patent ductus arteriosus	1.32	04
17	Hydrocephalus	1.65	05
18	Gigantism	1.32	04
19	Down syndrome	19.80	60
20	Posterior urethral valve	0.66	02
21	Edward syndrome	0.33	01
22	Diabetes	0.66	02
23	Polycystic kidney disease	1.65	05
24	Meningocele	2.97	09
25	Meningomyelocele	1.32	04
		100%	303

Figure No. 12: this graphical analysis shows the % prevalence of congenital diseases in district Mardan

Discussion

This study analyzed congenital disease prevalence in district Mardan, also its major types, causes, its relation to consanguinity, antenatal visits of mother in pregnancy, supplementation intake etc. Out of 10000 population 303 individuals have congenital diseases. A survey done by WHO, report that every year more than 300,000 infants born with congenital diseases. Worldwide prevalence of congenital malformation has been approximately 4 to 5%.

Among the disorders found in our survey in Mardan is about 2.31% i.e., 7 patients are affected with hydrops fetalis, 6 are of cleft palate which is about 1.98%, spina bifida patients are 2 (0.66%) in number found in the survey and anencephaly patients are 22 (7.26%) in number and 9 (2.97%) patients with meningocele disorder. According to (Butt *et al.*, 2013) 9 patients are diagnosed with anencephaly, 6 had hydrops fetalis disorder, 2 patients with cleft lip and with spina bifida, 1 with meningocele.

About 52.47% were male and 47.52% were female with congenital malformations, the male is more affected than female in our survey. Down syndromic patients are also found which are mostly in number, about 60 children. According to (Costa *et al.*, 2006) male are also more affected than female. 56.5% were male and 42.9% were female and one with indeterminate sex. The chromosomal abnormality was also found which was Down syndrome.

The consanguinity rate is 42.57% while folic acid usage is only 10.23% (taken regularly), 57.42% (not regularly) while 32.34% of individuals have not taken it all. The supplementation intake is in 10.23% regularly, in 57.42% not regularly while in 32.34% cases not taken at all. Study of (Khan *et al.*, 2015) demonstrated that

cousin marriages have a greater effect on the children. According to this study there are 61% of consanguineous marriages in Pakistan. The folic acid usage and multivitamins usage in according to that study was 32.3%.

The count of antenatal visits in pregnancy are almost not done regularly, about 8.91% mothers of affected individuals done antenatal checkups regularly, 75.24% have not done checkups regularly. According to (Roy *et al.*, 2016) about 92% pregnant women had irregular antenatal visits.

Bone abnormalities in affected individuals are deformed limbs 23.76%, short limbs 9.24% while 57.09% individuals with congenital anomalies have normal bone composition. According to (Farkhanda *et al.*, 2017) 36.2% congenital malformed children have abnormal musculoskeletal system followed by CNS (31.9%), the limb deformities are in 6.4% cases.

Most common disorders in our survey were neural disorders like microcephaly 8.91%, cerebral palsy 1.32%, hydrops fetalis 2.31%, meningocele 2.97% and meningomyelocele 1.32%.

Regular antenatal checkups and prenatal screening are best for prevention of congenital diseases but due to low socioeconomic level and poverty many females lack the process of treatment. They also do not take sufficient foods and supplementations like folic acids which are very useful and beneficial for the formation of brain and spinal cord. Mothers who got exposed to smoking, radiations, alcohol, and pesticides have greater chance of malformed babies. Women who previously had child of congenital disease have 2% risk of having a next child of congenital abnormality. Women who have history of neural tube defects babies should take folic acid milligram per day at least 4 weeks before another conception through first three months of pregnancy. Use of sodium valproate in pregnancy can also cause central nervous malformation in babies. According to our study 4.29% of women in their pregnancy took medications which are contraindicated in pregnancy.

Conclusion

Consanguinity and non-compliance with supplementation especially folic acid are associated risk factors responsible for congenital malformations. These malformations can be reduced by counseling the public regarding consanguineous marriages and folic acid supplementation during pregnancy. Public counseling should be provided through arranging seminars or by public speeches. Regular antenatal checkups and prenatal screening are recommended for early prevention and treatment. Male is more affected than female and existence of congenital malformations in family members is also dominated by male. Smoking is also one of the causes of poor maternal health, it affects the fetus inside the womb. A man with a genetic mutation on the X-chromosome is often affected by this condition because women have two copies of the X-chromosomes. Therefore X-rays are more common in men than women.

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